

INNOVATIVE WAYS TO INCREASE THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN THE COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the existing opportunities in the development of innovative technologies in the field of tourism. In particular, the level of use of Internet communication tools by potential consumers was studied, proposals were developed based on the results of research on the introduction of digital communications.

Keywords: Tourism, domestic and foreign tourism, competitiveness, innovation, investment, strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Being an important factor in mitigating the negative consequences of the global crisis in the context of the coronavirus pandemic, the development of the digital economy, which has suffered the most, requires focusing on such pressing issues as improving the competitiveness of the tourism sector. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted in his message to the Oliy Majlis, “We will continue consistent reforms in the field of tourism development in 2021. Special attention is paid to the development of pilgrimage tourism and domestic tourism in particular. Also, 1 trillion soums will be allocated from the budget to improve the land, water and road infrastructure around tourist sites”

ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Innovative competitiveness acts as a general indicator characterizing the innovative activity of the tourism industry. Because “innovation” and “competition” are closely related concepts. For example, M. Porter described innovation as a means of forming the forces of competition, R. Dole called innovation a weapon of global competition. Innovative aspects of competition theory were developed by J. Schumpeter, who characterized competition as “creative subversion” as competition with innovation, and introduced the terms “effective competition” and “effective monopoly” into the scientific exchange, which are related to the innovation process and entrepreneurial functions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the article is an analysis of resources, strategic development and competitiveness of the tourism sector, an analysis of the importance and role of the economy in accelerating the competitiveness of service sectors.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

“Innovative competitiveness” means the ability to gain a competitive advantage through innovation. That is, innovative competitiveness is the use of the existing innovative potential of the service sector and the degree of development of the innovation system in this area. Innovative competitiveness also means that service companies achieve a competitive advantage in terms of innovation by creating and providing innovative services.

The main feature of competition in the service sector and its sharp difference from industry and agriculture is that competition requires simultaneous consideration and analysis at several interrelated levels, including macro-, meso-, micro- and mono-levels. Only if competition at these levels can provide advantages, the synergetic effect of competitiveness in service and service provision will be obvious, new structural features of the industry will be formed. It is recommended to allocate the "7th" order of levels of innovative competitiveness in the service sector. These, in our opinion, include:

1. Innovative competitiveness of mega level (international prestige of new tourist services);
2. Innovative competitiveness at the macro level (national impact of new tourist services);
3. Innovative competitiveness at the meta-level (prestige of new tourist services at the industry and network level);
4. Innovative competitiveness at the meso-level (reputation of new tourist services at the regional and local level);

5. Innovative competitiveness at the micro-level (prestige of new tourist services among similar enterprises);

6. Innovative competitiveness at the mini-level (prestige of new tourist services from the point of view of families);

7. Innovative competitiveness at the macro-level (prestige of new tourist services from the point of view of individual and group consumers).

The creation of innovative projects is of great importance in increasing the innovative competitiveness of the tourism industry. The creation and implementation of an innovative project consists of three stages:

1) Pre-investment stage: determination of investment opportunities of the project; choose the latter based on the analysis of its alternatives; feasibility study; research support of the project, etc.

2) Investment stage: approval; conclusion of contracts; development of design and construction documentation; determine the project manager; staff training; review the preparation for launch.

3) Implementation stage: commissioning; bringing the project to full capacity; carrying out the costs of using existing capacities and updating fixed assets.

Innovative projects are divided into the following types according to the volume of tasks to be solved:

- mono-projects, as a rule, are designed to solve a single task, are carried out over a certain period of time, within certain financial resources and are coordinated by the project manager.

- multiprojects are an action program that includes dozens of single projects aimed at achieving a complex innovation goal related to the creation of a large scientific and technical complex and characterized by the need for a coordinating unit.

- megaprojects are multi—purpose complex programs that combine hundreds of mono-projects and several multi-projects interconnected to achieve a single goal, requiring centralized financing and management by a coordinating center.

The criteria for determining the success of innovative projects are as follows: financially successful; radical innovations; patent purity; protected by a license; priority areas of innovation; competitiveness of implemented innovations.

Thus, innovative competitiveness, on the one hand, reflects the real level of innovative development of the tourism industry, and on the other hand, serves as a measure of the effectiveness of the industry.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Strategic development of the tourism sector and increasing its competitiveness in order to achieve economic efficiency, first of all, it is necessary to clearly define the goals of the tourism sector, as well as the means and methods of achieving them. The

production of high-quality and competitive services at the lowest cost ensures maximum profit and avoids the crisis and is the main task of any tourism industry.

2. The need to increase its competitiveness is assessed on the basis of an analysis of trends and patterns of service provision and principles of strategic management. Since sustainability is the effectiveness of tourism activity, the realization of its competitive potential, and competitiveness is the effective use of the service capacities of the tourism sector and the definition of competitive service opportunities, taking into account the totality of these concepts allows the enterprise to formulate an optimal strategy to increase its competitiveness.

3. Improving the economic efficiency of tourism enterprises is one of the most important directions today. The demand of the population for tourism is increasing every year. To meet this demand, tourism enterprises need to apply innovative technologies, invest sufficient investments and improve mechanisms for using new effective methods.

- Uzbekistan tourism statistics for 2020 was **395,000,000.00**, a **76.47% decline** from 2019.

- Uzbekistan tourism statistics for 2019 was **1,679,000,000.00**, a **27.78% increase** from 2018.

- Uzbekistan tourism statistics for 2018 was **1,314,000,000.00**, a **57.37% increase** from 2017.

- Uzbekistan tourism statistics for 2017 was **835,000,000.00**, a **44.21% increase** from 2016

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Uzbekistan Tourism Statistics - Historical Data		
Year	Spending (\$)	% of Exports
2020	395,000,000.00	2.72
2019	1,679,000,000.00	9.88
2018	1,314,000,000.00	9.30
2017	835,000,000.00	6.73

Uzbekistan Tourism Statistics

International tourism receipts are expenditures by international inbound visitors, including payments to national carriers for international transport. These receipts include any other prepayment made for goods or services received in the destination country. They also may include receipts from same-day visitors, except when these are

important enough to justify separate classification. For some countries they do not include receipts for passenger transport items. Data are in current U.S. dollars.

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